

PRINCIPLES OF WORD SELECTION IN THEMATIC DICTIONARIES**Khojimirzayev Bekzodbek Ulugbek ugli**

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Abstract

This article analyzes the criteria for word selection in compiling thematic dictionaries, as well as their theoretical and practical foundations. In particular, the role of such criteria as semantic proximity, thematic relevance, frequency of use, communicative significance, and suitability for didactic purposes in selecting lexical units to be included in thematic dictionaries is highlighted. In addition, the issues of systematizing lexical material and taking into account users' needs in the process of creating thematic dictionaries are discussed. The results of the study contribute to improving the methodology of compiling thematic dictionaries.

Keywords: thematic dictionary, lexical unit, word selection criteria, semantic group, lexicography, didactic purpose, communicative approach, frequency of use, dictionary compilation methodology.

INTRODUCTION

In modern lexicography, thematic dictionaries play an important role as a means of systematically studying language units, grouping them according to specific themes, and presenting them in a user-friendly form for language learners. One of the main issues in compiling such dictionaries is the selection of words to be included in the dictionary based on scientifically grounded criteria. Indeed, the quality and practical value of a thematic dictionary directly depend on the relevance of the selected lexical units to the topic, their semantic integrity, and their communicative significance.

In the process of word selection, special attention should be paid to such factors as the frequency of lexical units, stylistic features, didactic value, and users' needs. Therefore, the scientific analysis of word selection criteria in thematic dictionaries is considered an actual issue for both theoretical and practical lexicography.

The purpose of this article is to identify the main criteria for word selection in thematic dictionaries and to highlight their role and importance in the lexicographic process.

PRINCIPLES OF WORD SELECTION

A thematic dictionary is a type of dictionary that systematically collects lexical units related to a specific topic, conceptual sphere, or semantic field. In such dictionaries, words are grouped not alphabetically but according to semantic proximity, logical connection, and thematic unity. This feature distinguishes thematic dictionaries from traditional explanatory, translation, or spelling dictionaries.

Thematic dictionaries are widely used as an important tool in language teaching methodology, translation studies, terminological research, and vocabulary development. In particular, when learning a foreign language or systematically mastering the vocabulary of one's native language, thematic dictionaries enable users to acquire lexical layers related to a particular topic comprehensively.

In lexicography, thematic dictionaries are of special importance in revealing the paradigmatic relations of language. They help to uncover semantic connections between words, lexical-semantic groups, and thematic layers. In this regard, thematic dictionaries serve as an important source not only for practical but also for theoretical lexicographic studies.

Today, thematic dictionaries are being developed not only in printed form but also in electronic and interactive formats. This expands their functional capabilities and increases their adaptability to users' needs.

The Role of Corpus Linguistics in Thematic Dictionary Compilation

Modern lexicography increasingly relies on corpus linguistics in the process of dictionary compilation. Language corpora provide authentic examples of word usage and help lexicographers identify the most frequent and communicatively important lexical units. In thematic dictionaries, corpus-based analysis allows researchers to determine which words are actively used within a particular semantic field.

For example, in compiling a thematic dictionary related to education, corpus analysis may reveal that words such as “online learning,” “digital classroom,” and “interactive platform” have become highly frequent in contemporary language use. As a result, thematic dictionaries should reflect current linguistic realities and include modern vocabulary relevant to users’ communicative needs.

In addition, corpus linguistics helps lexicographers avoid subjective word selection. Instead of relying only on intuition, dictionary compilers can use statistical data and real language materials. This increases the scientific reliability and practical value of thematic dictionaries.

In compiling thematic dictionaries, the general theoretical principles of lexicography serve as a methodological basis. In shaping dictionary content, it is necessary to take into account the lexical system of the language and its internal laws. In particular, such principles as semantic systematicity, functional relevance, communicative necessity, and user orientation form the theoretical foundation of thematic dictionary compilation.

The compilation of semantic dictionaries is considered one of the important directions of linguistics. Such dictionaries not only translate language units but also reveal their semantic features, scope of usage, and meaningful relations. Therefore, semantic precision and systematicity are regarded as key criteria in modern lexicography.

Professor Muxtorkhon Umarxo‘jayev in his work *General Linguistics* interprets language as a system expressing the thinking and culture of society. According to the scholar, language units are interconnected through semantic relations, and this aspect is of great importance in dictionary compilation.

In creating semantic dictionaries, it is important to correctly explain the semantic features of words because each word expresses a certain concept, idea, and cultural meaning. From this point of view, a dictionary is not only a translation tool but also a spiritual and educational source. The descriptive-thematic dictionaries created by Muxtorkhon Umarxo‘jayev are significant because they serve as an effective methodological basis for learning foreign languages. According to the scholar’s views, paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations of language units should be taken into account in dictionary compilation. This helps reveal the interconnections between words. As a result, users understand not only the meaning of a word but also its possibilities of use in speech.

Furthermore, semantic dictionaries are an important means of enriching young people’s vocabulary, developing their thinking, and learning foreign languages. In particular, descriptive and thematic dictionaries strengthen learners’ memorization abilities. Therefore, the use of modern pedagogical approaches in dictionary compilation is considered one of the urgent issues today.

According to the principle of semantic systematicity, the lexical units included in the dictionary should be semantically related and form a certain semantic field. This ensures the internal logical integrity of the thematic dictionary. For example, a dictionary related to the theme “education” may include semantically connected units such as school, teacher, textbook, classroom, and examination.

When classifying words by themes, the lexical-semantic system of the language, especially paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations, is also of great importance. Paradigmatic relations include semantic connections such as synonymy, antonymy, hypernymy, and hyponymy, allowing systematic grouping of dictionary units. Syntagmatic relations, on the other hand,

reflect the combinational possibilities of words in speech and determine their practical sphere of usage.

In addition, the anthropocentric approach is considered an important theoretical basis in modern lexicography. According to this approach, the user's age, language proficiency level, professional needs, and communicative goals should be taken into account when compiling dictionaries.

Indeed, the practical effectiveness of a dictionary depends on its user-oriented model.

User-Oriented Approach in Modern Lexicography

One of the main tendencies in modern lexicography is the user-oriented approach. According to this principle, dictionaries should be designed in accordance with the needs, language level, age, and professional interests of users. A thematic dictionary intended for school students differs significantly from a dictionary created for translators or linguists.

User-oriented thematic dictionaries usually contain simplified definitions, visual illustrations, example sentences, and semantic groupings that facilitate vocabulary acquisition. In electronic dictionaries, interactive functions such as audio pronunciation, hyperlinks, and search systems further improve the effectiveness of dictionary use.

Therefore, considering the target audience is one of the essential requirements in selecting lexical units for thematic dictionaries.

Thus, the theoretical foundations of word selection in thematic dictionaries are closely connected with the semantic system of language, lexical relations, and user-oriented lexicographic approaches.

The selection of lexical units in thematic dictionaries is based on several criteria:

Semantic proximity;

Thematic relevance;

Frequency of use;

Communicative significance;

Suitability for didactic purposes.

In practice, a number of theoretical and practical problems arise during the compilation of thematic dictionaries. One of these shortcomings is the inclusion of units that are not directly related to the topic or are semantically peripheral. Such cases may disrupt the thematic integrity of the dictionary and create an unclear understanding of the topic for users.

Another important problem concerns the disordered or unexplained placement of synonymous units. If synonyms are presented without indicating their stylistic, emotional, or functional differences, users may not correctly understand their usage. This can lead to communicative errors, especially for language learners.

Moreover, insufficient consideration of the users' age, level of knowledge, professional needs, and goals reduces the effectiveness of thematic dictionaries. For example, including complex terminological units in a dictionary intended for beginner learners decreases its didactic value.

In addition, some dictionaries select lexical units without considering their frequency of use and actual activity in speech. As a result, rarely used or obsolete words may replace actively used vocabulary. This reduces the communicative value of the dictionary.

Therefore, strict adherence to scientific criteria, analysis of the target audience, and careful selection of lexical units are important conditions for ensuring the quality of thematic dictionaries.

Digital Technologies and Electronic Thematic Dictionaries

The rapid development of digital technologies has significantly influenced modern dictionary compilation. Electronic thematic dictionaries provide users with faster access to lexical information and allow continuous updating of vocabulary materials. Unlike printed dictionaries, electronic resources can integrate multimedia elements such as images, sound recordings, animations, and interactive exercises.

Digital thematic dictionaries are especially effective in foreign language teaching. Visual and

audio materials help learners memorize vocabulary more efficiently and improve pronunciation skills. Furthermore, online dictionaries make it possible to search lexical items instantly and organize them according to semantic categories.

Consequently, the integration of digital technologies into lexicography contributes to the modernization and practical efficiency of thematic dictionaries.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the process of word selection in thematic dictionaries is one of the most important stages determining their scientific and practical value.

Applying such criteria as semantic proximity, thematic relevance, frequency of use, communicative significance, and suitability for didactic purposes improves the quality of dictionaries. At the same time, the needs of the target audience and the field of dictionary application should also be taken into consideration. The use of corpus technologies and electronic resources in modern lexicography provides opportunities for further improving the process of thematic dictionary compilation. The consistent application of these criteria contributes to the creation of scientifically grounded, practically effective, and user-friendly thematic dictionaries.

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